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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 6.4 – INTEGRATED THEIA^{XR} TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODOLOGIES AND USE CASE IMPLEMENTATION (FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

This deliverable describes the integration activities performed within the three use cases since the previous deliverable D6.1. Majority of the integration work has been finalized, but some final integration activities will take place to do the last testing, demonstrating and validation. The technology development work coming from work packages 3 till 5 is done, technologies and prototypes are available for final testing and validation within the real-life demonstrators and in the real dedicated environments. To perform these final tests and validations, the first versions were integrated already in the real demonstrators, but also in lab demonstrators. For the final demonstrators, these solutions will be integrated into the final real demonstrators.

This document provides details about the latest and final integration activities, including the different infrastructures available at the mobile machinery (i.e., snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator) and how the final prototypes and technologies are integrated into the infrastructures of the machines. Compared to the first deliverables, where most of the developed solutions were standalone, during the final phase of the project most of the solutions are fully integrated into the machinery to aid the human operators.

Each section highlights the different technologies and their status for integration. Most of the technologies are already integrated into the actual machines, whereas some of them are in the final stage of being integrated on the machines, which will be described in detail how they will be integrated. This deliverable is the basis for the final work to be performed in work package 6, which will focus on the final testing, demonstration and validation of the individual methodologies and technologies.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable D6.4 summarizes the work that has been performed in the second and last cycle of Task 6.1, related to the individual components and methodologies, and their interfaces in the three dedicated use cases of THEIA^{XR}.

The aim of Task 6.1 is to implement and integrate the applications and technologies coming from the technical work packages WP3 – WP5, into the use cases. The first integration steps were documented in deliverable D6.1, where the first prototypes where the applications and technologies were either modified to fit the actual demonstrators (i.e., the snow groomer, reach stacker or the excavator) or potentially deployed with simulated environment potentially using simulated data. The final integration in the real demonstrators has been performed in the second phase of the integration, which is described in this deliverable. Unfortunately, the integration phase has not finished with Month 30 in the project and final activities are still taking place. The last and final integration activities will be reported in the last deliverables of WP6, which are deliverables D6.5 and D6.6. The focus has been mainly on integrating the final prototypes and developments in the real demonstrators and going largely beyond the simulated environments. The actual demonstration of the solutions with the use cases and the real environment is performed in Task 6.2 and the evaluation of the technologies and methodologies is accomplished in Task 6.3.

The work package 6 brings all the work from the other work packages together, but also provided feedback to all the other (technical) work packages (as can be seen in Figure 1). The use cases are specified in work package 2, which also defines the (technical) requirements for the technologies being developed in work packages 3-5. These work packages provided the technologies and methodologies that is finally integrated into the demonstrators, which happened in work package 6. Additionally, the results that came out of work package 6 flowed back into the technical work packages and into the specifications, resulting in the final use case descriptions and improved technologies.

Figure 1: Work Package interaction within THEIA^{XR}

Deliverable D6.4 will therefore provide the final version of the integrated solutions and applied methodologies and the final releases of the technologies coming from WP3-WP5, based on the requirements and specifications defined in WP2. Additionally, it will provide the final implementations of the use case applications and services.

In the following chapter, the three different use cases are considered separately, highlighting the final infrastructure, the technologies integrated and the remaining open work to be performed for the specific use case that is being discussed, which is discussed in Section 2.1 (Use Case 1), Section 2.2 (Use Case 2) and Section 2.3 (Use Case 3). Finally, the deliverable is concluded in chapter 3.

2 Use Case Implementation

In the following three subsections, the integration activities within the three use cases (snow grooming, logistics and construction) will be described. It will start with an overview of the final infrastructure that is being used within the mobile machines (snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator). Afterwards, the latest and final step of integration of the different methodologies and technologies will be described. Each subsection will be finalized with a description of the still required activities and the lessons learned during the integration activities.

2.1 Use Case 1 – Snow Grooming

2.1.1 UC1 Infrastructure

Infrastructure involved in the research and development activities regarding use case 1 comprised two interaction labs, Tu Graz und TUD. Research and Testing in the interaction Labs were used to prototype the light feedback, projection and spotlight technology. Further visuals for ground projection and adaptable XR were tested as well in the context of snow grooming operation scenarios using XR output hardware in simulated and real work environments and sensor data.

For implementations, a dedicated area in the Prinoth facility is provided, which allows all partner to integrate XR technologies and required sensors into Prinoth equipment. A state-of-the-art snow groomer is provided as well as a fully equipped operator cabin to perform the integration works.

Depending on the time of implementation and availability, the demonstrator snow groomer, may not always be the same, but in case the research content will be transferred. A ski area and a cross-country skiing centre in the vicinity of Sterzing, Italy is available for testing in real environment. It is ensured that for both real-world location a summer scan of the terrain exists and therefore an accurate digital terrain model is available. Additionally, a target surface has been designed and integrated. Prinoth experts and the ski resorts helped us with feedback, domain expertise and participants for co-creation workshops and evaluation testing.

The snow groomer is equipped with a telematic box to track vehicle data and an accurate snow measurement system, based on GNSS RTK to track the exact localization and orientation of the vehicle. Data can be retrieved via the CAN interface, allowing for real-time monitoring and analysis.

Prototype technologies are initially tested in outdoor environments to evaluate their functionality under potentially extreme weather conditions. During this phase, control and monitoring are conducted via a separate laptop, as full integration into the snow groomer is not yet implemented. The focus is on assessing the durability and performance of the prototypes when exposed to real environmental factors.

In later stages, haptic feedback systems are integrated into the original hardware wherever feasible, enabling direct comparison with the standard controls. Visual display options within the snow groomer's driver cabin are also incorporated to enhance the realism and usability of the system.

To ensure the highest level of realism, the operator cabin used as a standalone demonstrator is an original Leitwolf cabin. It features a center seat for the operator and two additional seats to accommodate test instructors and observers. The human-machine interface (HMI) is arranged and adjustable to replicate the configuration of the actual machine.

To make the best possible use of the available cabin and the simulation, both systems were combined. For this purpose, a screen is positioned in front of the cabin. The simulation allows the driver to operate a snow groomer in a simulated environment; one of the test areas was digitally replicated for this purpose. The simulated snow groomer is operated in the cabin by using the original controls. In addition, some XR technologies are integrated into the cabin to obtain initial feedback from the drivers. For this purpose, an LED around the windscreen, a separate display, an LED around the display, the steering lever and the joystick are integrated, each with haptic feedback. Technologies such as light projections on the snow surface are integrated directly into the simulation. The cabin itself is mounted on a steel structure, allowing to be moved using a crane or forklift.

This comprehensive infrastructure and phased testing approach provide a robust foundation for the development and validation of innovative technologies in snow grooming operations, ensuring that the solutions are both technically sound and practically applicable.

2.1.2 Integrated Technologies/Methodologies

2.1.2.1 Application of Co-Design Methodology in UC1

Following the user research conducted in Sterzing, Italy, as part of T3.1 (see Figure 2), a problem scenario was defined (first step of the scenario-based design approach), describing a current typical snow-grooming operation. This scenario was shared with the consortium. On October 19, 2023, an ideation workshop was held involving all active partners in this use-case. In this workshop, ideas for technology usage and some concepts already in development were collected and discussed in terms of their technical feasibility and expected utility for the operators. It was assumed that operators may have difficulties coming up with technology usage and interaction ideas on their own and may both over- and underestimate what is currently technically possible. Thus, the input from project partners was going to be implemented into a first activity scenario version, providing examples of how XR technology could realistically support operators at work and serving as a basis for the idea generation and validation with operators.

The activity scenarios, as defined in [1], were internally dubbed “vision scenarios” to highlight their purpose as ideal interaction concepts, outlining the goals of development. During the internal review of the initial UC1 ideation workshop’s results, the current spectrum of ideas was found to be rather realism-centered, focusing on mostly feasible solutions. To include some more visionary, speculative ideas as well, it was considered necessary to create two vision scenarios for each use case, one *realistic* cabin-based version, aimed at being more achievable and possibly market-ready within a few years after conclusion of the project, and one *futuristic* version, aimed at being more ambitious but possibly achievable within a larger timespan of 5 – 10 years after conclusion of the project.

Figure 2: Picture from the UC1 user research in Sterzing, where researchers were able to accompany the operators in their vehicles to gain insights.

The first version of a realistic and futuristic vision scenario for UC1 were completed and shared with the consortium in January 2024. Subsequently, the planning of co-design workshops with operators started in coordination with PRIN, UL, HAP and TUG, which were going to attend the co-design workshops with

operators in UC1 along with HdM from the consortium side. The first stage of co-design workshops, focusing on validating and expanding planned technological features (e. g., the smart spotlight or outer lane border projections), was completed in February 2024. The next stage of co-design workshops for UC1, validation and elaboration of information design concepts, was completed in April 2024.

This stage resulted in text-based information scenarios, complemented by wireframes (rough visualisations of XR- and screen-based information), partly using screenshots from Creanex' simulation environment. The final stage of the scenario-based co-design approach involved the ideation and validation of positive user experience (PUX) concepts and providing safety-critical design recommendations in the final integrated interaction scenarios (see deliverable D3.7). This stage was completed within a final workshop in July 2025 (see Figure 3). With the finalization of deliverable D3.7, the scenario-based co-design process (task T3.2) has concluded in UC1, final work on the prototypes is being done (task T3.4) and evaluations (task T3.5) are in progress.

Figure 3: Concept validation workshop with operators in Sterzing, July 2025

2.1.2.2 Identifying Privacy Requirements and Strategies for Mitigating Privacy and Ethical Risks in Implementations in UC1

To identify the possible risks for privacy and ethics in UC1 we used the following technologies:

- A series of questions in the semi-structured interviews [4] with the operators were performed in the frames of co-design workshops and conducted in the frames of T3.1. The questions for the semi-structured interview were developed in line with an iterative design approach and followed the purpose of understanding end-users' perception of the data generated by the operation in terms of usefulness for their work and their will to share the data with external entities. The questions were also designed to understand the general privacy concerns of the operators and their perception of the future workflow, including the perception of the factors of automatization of the operations and new data modalities provided by XR.
- Based on the UC1 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.1.2.1), we developed and conducted two iterative [9] workshops with the end-users using the approach based on value-sensitive design [2]. In the first workshop, we proposed to the end-users the list of Schwartz values [6] and discussed with them the importance of these values to their work; in addition, we tested the perception of each technology, validated in the frames of co-design, in the dimensions of usefulness, ease of use (subdomains of Technology Acceptance Model [1]), security/safety [7] and excitement([5]). On the second stage, based on the most important values, we started to discuss how the violation

of these values in design can affect the perception of the work and what should be done in the scenario to ensure that this "anti-scenario" (negative scenario of use technology [3]) will not take place. As the technological evaluations are taking place in Autumn 2025, in the last step of the co-design of privacy mechanisms, we are planning to prototype the two mechanisms, which can support the values of autonomy and security on the interface level and make the final user evaluation of the concepts in November 2025.

- Based on the UC1 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.1.2.1), we developed a survey of privacy questions for the stakeholders regarding each of the proposed changes in the basic workflow, using the principles of Data Protection Impact Assessment. The questionnaire helped identify the most privacy-critical parts of the proposed technology development and added privacy concerns to the discussion about the feasibility of proposed solutions. Besides eliciting GDPR-related requirements, we applied the LINDDUN GO methodology [8] to elicit a broader range of technical and non-technical privacy concerns from stakeholders. To do that, we organised two privacy workshops with representatives of UC1 and technological partners involved in UC1. The results helped identify the most privacy-controversial technologies with the proposals for mitigating the possible privacy risks. In addition, we conducted the focus-group with the members of the consortium, involved in the use cases specifically dedicated to the use of AI in the project, based on the methodology of Z-Inspection [10], dedicated to specifically mapping the risks posed to the AI use in the project. Also based on the work with the end-users and other stakeholders, described in D7.4 we designed the list of Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Designing the XR implementations (all three use cases); we present these preliminary results in several workshops/focus-groups to the external auditory, involved in the similar European Projects to gather their feedback and developed and conduct two workshops with the partners, involved in the project to validate and refine the content of the Guidelines. The refined version of the Guidelines will be evaluated with the stakeholders at the start of September 2026.

2.1.2.3 Information Requirements and Multimodal Interaction Concepts

The development of industrial user interfaces aims to achieve optimal interaction between technical systems and human operators in the context of specific work tasks and conditions to achieve superior productivity and safety. In such use cases, XR technologies are considered most effective when they are used to combine real world information with digital data in a way and at a place where it contributes to the operators' information requirements, closely bound to their mental processing procedures involving perception, evaluation/reasoning, and decision making based on optimal situation awareness.

To complement human-focused requirement analysis, integration of XR-Technologies followed a second, analytical approach in this project for which we developed an extended analysis framework for XR application (see Deliverable 4.7) that put special emphasis on investigated correspondence between real-world-based information and digital information indicating a potentially useful combination through augmentation. This approach focused on (1) **identifying information requirements** involved in machine operation, (2) **attention constraints within operation workflows**, and (3) **interaction opportunities and constraints of specific XR technologies** to define effective means of information augmentation (what information on what modality?) in **multimodal interaction concepts**. Insights as documented in final-version Deliverables 4.1, 4.6., and 4.8. regarding UC1 are summarized below.

Information requirements were analysed with a couple of analysis activities including a **system analysis** of snow groomers that identified high level goals, associated machine functions, and information (see Deliverable 4.1 and 4.3). Analysis resulted in a comprehensive list of information and interaction requirements for snow groomer machine control and operation activities based on identified high level goals (Task fulfilment/effectivity, Machine efficiency, Ensure Safety and Machine operability). For UC1, these requirements comprise of for example information about (hidden) objects in the vicinity (amount, orientation, distance, type, and movement of the obstacles), surface and area information (e.g. snow depth, slope borders), maps and 3D-data of target slope geometry, processing quality (slope surface quality), and information about the position and configuration of the tool (e.g., blade, tiller) to precisely realizing the target

geometry. Conventional approaches in snow groomer operation require operators to use direct sight on the environment and blade, but also digital information such as maps, 3D data, and tool position information, presented on the terminal display to inform themselves about the accuracy of their current vehicle and tool movement.

Attention constraints were identified by conducting **analysis of operation tasks** in snow grooming revealing significant amounts of attention allocation lay on four attention hot spots: (1) the terrain ahead, (2) the blade, (3) the terminal displays, and (4) the joysticks/vibration/sound in the cabin, that provide haptic feedback about the machines load. Operators continuously shift attention between these in operation procedures.

Opportunities and Constraints of XR technologies were assessed in discussing technical capabilities of specific XR technologies regarding their capabilities to effectively augment real world information and digital data at attentional hot spots in these operation scenarios. Thus, we aimed to use XR technologies to bring as much digital information to the environment as possible. Accounting for the identified areas of attention allocation in the snow grooming use case, we explored five XR technologies and their information presentation and interaction **capabilities and constraints**:

- **Light Feedback System:** Peripheral light feedback brings the opportunity to communicate low-complex information from outside the attention focus area. Different spatial setups were explored finding that ambient light feedback from a light strip around the windshield could be used to indicate position, distance, and type of detected obstacles, as well as indicating distance between tool and planned slope geometry. Light feedback is very limited regarding the complexity of information that can be conveyed, needs to be adjusted to environmental light conditions and can distract the operator.
- **Laser Projection:** Dynamic and spatially mapped laser projections in the environment offer the capability to present high complex graphical information directly at point of interest. We found that such visualizations can be used to visualize snow depth, 3D geometry data (e.g. deviation from target surface profile) as a coloured grid or a linear cross section as well as to visualize planned movement paths, navigation instructions, planned slope geometry and tool position offsets. However, laser projections are limited in brightness and higher levels of brightness come with increased safety risks (blindness).
- **Spotlight:** Bright and directed spotlights offer the opportunity to highlight and illuminate smaller areas and objects in the environment. We found that this XR modality can be useful to raise awareness towards moving and static objects (e.g., skiers, tree lines, buildings, poles, holes). On the downside, spotlights need to be calibrated to environmental illumination to avoid glare (especially critical in white snow environments) of the operator, humans and cameras on the machine and in the environment. Also, spotlights are very limited regarding the complexity of conveyed information and are less effective in low visibility conditions (e.g., fog, rain, snowfall).
- **Display AR:** Terminal displays offer the opportunity to augment video streams and virtual 3D models blending virtual data with real world information cues. We found that display-based augmentation might be useful to augment video streams stemming from an array of conventional and thermal cameras with information from object detection algorithms to provide better visibility of obstacles. Overlaying data from a virtual 3D-model that visualizes current and target surface geometry camera streams as well as augmenting virtual 3D models with live LiDAR data can help operators to understand such digital information. Augmented video streams can also be used to present interactive quality assessments regarding the processed surface behind the snow groomer. Limitations in using display-based augmentation lay in the fact, that operators need to divert their attention from the real environment to the terminal display.

- **Haptic control feedback:** Haptic feedback in the snow groomers track controls and joystick offer the opportunity to present feedback cues at a place where the operator has its hands most of the time. We found that this XR modality can be used to inform operators about required or restricted machine and tool movements. Further, haptic and force feedback on physical controls can reinforce or reproduce machine behaviour, which can also be used to inform the snow groomer operator about limits in machine and tool movement or alignment with target machine movement paths and blade positions.

As a Result, a list of requirements covering information presentation items and interaction items were collected that are involved in defined tasks, machine functions and conditions. For these items, further attributes, such as importance, attentional focus, and preferable means of XR were collected to provide a structured and systematic basis for discussing effectivity and benefits of XR functions and interaction design approaches that aim to improve ease of use, usability and performance as crucial factors for overall technology acceptance.

Based on these insights, **multimodal interaction concepts** defined interaction and information presentation modalities that combine specific real-world information and digital data at distinct places in the cabin-based control environment. The conducted analysis highlighted the problem of increasing complexity and importance of display-based information while environment-based or backed information also stays important forcing the operator to constantly shift attention. Combining different modalities in XR features aims to help to reduce the ease of use and complexity of display-based interfaces or to move information from display-based interfaces to environmental perception. In exploring this design space in between information requirements and XR technology opportunities we defined a final interaction concept for UC1 that comprises the following features:

- **Light-Feedback Systems** [Lab/SIM, Machine] were realized to cover the forward windscreen and the terminal display to provide peripheral information, when looking onto the blade and environment as well as when interacting with the terminal display. This XR modality is used to present information regarding detected objects (above and sub-surface) in the environment and deviation of blade position to target surface geometry. Objects are visualized as light indications highlighting the direction (as by position on the light strip) and distance (as by the colour of the light indication). Position deviations are represented as linear bars in vertical and horizontal orientation to show distance in rotation and depth of the tool.
- **Ground Projections**, [Lab/SIM, Machine] are used to explore effective visualization techniques to present, navigational aids, snow depth, surface deviation from target geometry as well as detected above and sub-surface objects. Navigation aids can be visualized as instructions (distance, direction), paths and area boarders. Snow depth can be visualized as a projected cross-section. Instructions, paths and boarders can be visualized as graphics (arrows, numeric indicators, lines and shaded shapes).
- **Spotlight** [Machine] devices mounted on the cabin are used to show information in the environment to enhance operators view when monitoring the area in front of the machine. This XR modality is used to present information regarding detected objects (above surface). Objects are targeted with the light beam to highlight their position in the environment. The spotlight utilizes data from object detection systems to distinguish humans and other objects and humans are addressed with a less bright and non-continuous light up to avoid glare. Spotlight brightness can also be adapted to avoid glare of the operator.
- **AR Display Visualizations** [Lab/ Machine] are used to highlight detected objects, navigation instructions, tool position and load charts in available video streams.
- **Haptic control feedback** [Lab] is realized to provide vibratory feedback signals in the machine's track controls that indicate warning and navigation instructions.
- **Adaptable XR techniques** [Lab] are realized to explore usefulness of giving operators the ability to navigate across the spectrum between full reality and maximum augmentation with virtual information to account for different situational and individual requirements. Two approaches to

adaptation controls were conceptualized: (1) a GUI-based setup environment that operators can use to manipulate the XR features, and (2) a set of hardware controls placed in the cabin. Both approaches allow operators to change the presentation of augmenting data on each XR output device regarding virtuality/reality (e.g. though changing opacity or brightness), level of detail and coverage of assistive systems (e.g., obstacle detection, target slope geometry).

2.1.2.4 Development of an iterative Methodology for Implementation of envisioned XR Functions

In the scope of task T4.4 “Multimodal interaction concepts and resulting requirements for XR-Technology and UI”, we developed a method to translate vision scenarios resulting from the co-design process into functional specifications for UI control and feedback functions, which serve as the basis for engineering implementations of these functions. The approach was devised and put into practice with respect to the design of immersive simulation demonstrators of these functions, however the functional specifications for the simulator functions can just as well serve as a basis for engineering real-world implementations of control and feedback functions for integration into vehicles, as is the focus of work package WP6. The approach spans all three THEIA^{XR} use-cases and thus will not be further discussed in Sections 2.2 and 2.3. Please refer to deliverables D4.4 “Interaction Concepts (first version)” for more details on the devised methodology and to deliverable D4.8 “Interaction Concepts (final version)” for the final set of control and feedback function specifications which were devised following this approach.

Figure 4: Methodology for establishing the list of control and feedback functions of interest

This methodology is the same for use-cases UC2 and UC3 and its description will thus not be repeated in Sections 2.2 and 2.3 below.

2.1.2.5 Identifying Privacy Requirements and Strategies for Mitigating Privacy and Ethical Risks in Implementations in UC1

To identify the possible risks for privacy and ethics in UC1 we used the following technologies:

- A series of questions in the semi-structured interviews [5] with the operators were performed in the frames of co-design workshops and conducted in the frames of T3.1. The questions for the semi-structured interview were developed in line with an iterative design approach and followed the purpose of understanding end-users’ perception of the data generated by the operation in terms of usefulness for their work and their will to share the data with external entities (like the company or the developer of the solution). The questions were also designed to understand the general privacy concerns of the operators and their perception of the future workflow, including the perception of the factors of automatization of the operations and new data modalities provided by XR.

- Based on the UC1 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.1.2.1), we developed and conducted two iterative [10] workshops with the end-users using the approach based on value-sensitive design [3]. In the first workshop, we proposed to the end-users the list of Schwartz values [7] and discussed with them the importance of these values to their work as snow groomer operator, using the fictional snow groomer operator persona; in addition, we tested the perception of each technology, validated in the frames of co-design, in the dimensions of usefulness, ease of use (subdomains of Technology Acceptance Model [2]), security/safety [8] and enjoyment/excitement([6]) based on the theoretical assumption of the importance of these values in the development of industrial XR context. On the second stage, based on the most important values, we started to discuss how the violation of these values in design can affect the perception of the work and what should be done in the scenario to ensure that this "anti-scenario" (negative scenario of use technology [4]) will not take place. As the technological evaluations are taking place in Autumn 2025, in the last step of the co-design of privacy mechanisms, we are planning to prototype the two mechanisms, which can support the values of autonomy and security on the interface level and make the final user evaluation of the concepts in November 2025.
- Based on the UC1 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.1.2.1), we developed a survey of privacy questions for the stakeholders regarding each of the proposed changes in the basic workflow, using the principles of Data Protection Impact Assessment. The questionnaire helped identify the most privacy-critical parts of the proposed technology development and added privacy concerns to the discussion about the feasibility of proposed solutions. Besides eliciting GDPR-related requirements, we applied the LINDDUN GO methodology [9] to elicit a broader range of technical and non-technical privacy concerns from stakeholders. To do that, we organised two privacy workshops with representatives of UC1 and technological partners involved in UC1. The results helped identify the most privacy-controversial technologies with the proposals for mitigating the possible privacy risks. In addition, we conducted the focus-group with the members of the consortium, involved in the use cases specifically dedicated to the use of AI in the project, based on the methodology of Z-Inspection [11] dedicated to specifically mapping the risks posed to the AI use in the project. Also based on the work with the end-users and other stakeholders, described in D7.4 we designed the list of Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Designing the XR implementations (all three UC's); we present these preliminary results in several workshops/focus-groups to the external auditory, involved in the similar European Projects to gather their feedback and developed and conduct two workshops with the partners, involved in the project to validate and refine the content of the Guidelines. The refined version of the Guidelines will be evaluated with the stakeholders at the start of September 2026

2.1.2.6 Integration of Use-Case Specific Joystick Handles with Haption Force-Feedback Devices

Because the vehicles considered in THEIA^{XR} present complex control layouts on the joysticks that are highly specific to each use-case and vehicle, it was necessary to devise a way of interfacing the vehicle standard joysticks with the primary haptic device designed by Haption. To this end, we leveraged the combined mechanical and 10-pole electrical connector present on all Haption force-feedback devices and designed a custom interface for connecting it respectively to an adapter built around an original Prinoth Leitwolf joystick handle and a custom-built handle built for use-case UC2 which mimics the ergonomics of a reachstacker joystick (see also deliverable D5.6 *"Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (final version)"* for design details).

Figure 5: Use-case specific joystick handles and common electrical-mechanical connector

For the UC1 joystick handle, this involved disassembling an original Prinoth Leitwolf joystick to remove the mechanical assembly for the rotary joints in its base and rewiring the CAN controller in its base to a custom cable allowing us to route all joystick button signals directly to the Prinoth Control Unit via its original CAN connector, bypassing the Haptics ECU. On the other hand, the addon built onto the handle incorporates the deadman switch required for safe operation of the haptic device, as well as the vibrotactile actuator (discussed below in Section 2.1.2.7) and its silicone damping element.

This integration work overlaps both use-cases UC1 and UC2, we will thus not repeat its description in Section 2.2.2 below.

2.1.2.7 Integration of Off-The-Shelf Vibrotactile Actuators with Force-Feedback Devices

In order to realize the feedback functions requiring vibrotactile notifications to be provided at the joystick and track control handles, it was necessary to integrate off-the-shelf vibrotactile actuators with existing Haption force-feedback devices. Ultimately, this approach led to the design of force-feedback device handles with a built-in vibrotactile actuators as described in deliverable D5.6 “*Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (final version)*”.

Deliverable D5.5 “*Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (first version)*” describes in detail the initial prototyping tests which were conducted to select a suitable method for delivering wide-range vibration feedback through the device handles (see also Figure 6 below). In the end, the Titan Haptics TacHammer Carlton¹ linear magnetic ram actuator was chosen due to its versatility, ease of integration, and sufficient vibration intensity for the applications considered.

¹ <https://titanhaptics.com/carlton/>

Figure 6: Early prototyping work for integration of vibrotactile actuators with force feedback device handles

During the mechanical design iterations for the THEIA^{XR} use-case handles and the track controls unit, we realised that ensuring proper mechanical isolation of the vibrotactile actuators was essential to ensure that the vibrations could be properly felt regardless of operator grip strength and that the vibrations do not unnecessarily propagate to the rest of the structure of the haptic input devices. To ensure that these requirements were fulfilled, we evaluated multiple options for damping and converged towards a design of silicone damper sleeves for the vibrotactile actuator housings in the different handles (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Testbench (left) and lever prototypes (right) for testing various damping elements (in this case for the haptic track control handles)

To drive the actuator, off-the-shelf haptic drivers by Texas Instruments² were selected as these provide an I²C interface to trigger and generate tactile cues. We designed two driver boards using these drivers and Arduino micro microcontroller boards, one for the single actuator in the primary haptic device handle and one for the dual actuators present in the track control levers. A custom firmware was written for these controllers, allowing a high-level controller (the Haptics ECU in the case of UC1 and the simulation PC in the case of UC2) to trigger a set of vibrotactile patterns via USB. Deliverable D5.6 “*Multimodal Immersive cockpit (final version)*” describes the electronics in more detail, while the software architecture and vibrotactile cue library are described in deliverable D4.8 “*Interaction Concepts (final version)*”

² <https://www.ti.com/product/DRV2605>

Figure 8: Dedicated 2-channel vibrotactile controller designed for the haptic track controls unit

Figure 9 shows the final design of the handles for the primary haptic device, respectively for use-case UC1 (Center) and use-case UC2 (Right). Figure 9 shows the final handle design for the haptic track controls unit in use-case UC1 (Right).

Figure 9: Final design of the handles for the haptic track controls

2.1.2.8 Snow Groomer Simulator

The snow groomer simulator development was focused on integrating the technologies from other partners into the simulator. In practice this means that the simulator transmits information of the machine and surrounding virtual objects via CAN to the central processor, and the integrated technologies then use this data to react to the virtual surroundings.

The simulator was used to demonstrate the project in InterAlpin trade fair. Because the demonstrator included the entire physical snow groomer cabin, a special version of the simulator was made where the simulator only shows the outside of the cabin. The simulated cabin, mirrors and virtual control devices were hidden in the simulator, because they already existed physically.

The simulator was connected to the actual control devices of the snow groomer via CAN. Joystick and pedals were used to drive the snow groomer and control the front blade position. These are the same devices as are used in real snow groomers.

Animated skiers were set to go past the snow groomer periodically while the demonstrator users were driving the snow groomer. The simulator transmitted the positions of these skiers via CAN to the central processor. A physical ambient LED bar made by TUD received this obstacle data and reacted to the skiers in the simulator. It visualised the direction of the virtual obstacles around the snow groomer by showing lights in the direction of the obstacle. The distance between obstacle and machine was visualised by the size and colour of the warning, small green light for distant obstacles, and large red light for close obstacles.

The simulator can also be controlled with a haptic feedback joystick developed by Haption. The communications between haptic joystick and simulator work via CAN. The information about obstacles is sent to the haptic joystick, and the joystick vibrates when obstacles are coming closer to warn the user. Alternatively, a UDP network connection was configured between the simulator and haptic controllers to make the data connection easier and more user-friendly during testing and development.

A driving training was implemented to the snow groomer. A route with checkpoints can be defined on the terrain. Markers on the edges of the route and a laser-projected green arrow indicate the path for the operator. The simulator transmits the current machine position, direction and the next gate position, so it can be calculated if the machine is being driven in the right direction and if the deviation from the centre line of the path is too large. The haptic joystick uses this information to warn the user if they are straying from the target route. When the driver reaches the finish, the driving route is shown as a 2D image for the operator to review.

Figure 10: Driving path with gates and guide arrow

Multiple different weather and lighting scenarios were implemented to the simulator in the Ladurns terrain model. The user can toggle between different levels of fog and lighting levels: from clear skies to very dense fog with only few meters of visibility, and from clear daylight to midnight darkness. The simulated snow groomer has position lights, low beams, high beams and a spotlight that can be toggled on and off independently of each other. The user can also move a spotlight to illuminate a small patch of their surroundings in any direction. The assistive technologies developed in the project are most useful and make the biggest difference in difficult visibility conditions, so it was important to make simulator be able to simulate them.

Figure 11: Outside view on clear night

Figure 12: Very foggy daylight view from cockpit

Figure 13: Spotlight pointing towards incoming skier

A virtual version of the ambient LED bar is implemented into the snow groomer simulator. It detects obstacles around the machine and visualises their distance and direction by showing warning lights on the edges of the windscreen. It works similarly to the physical version developed by TUD.

Figure 14: Led bar warning of a close obstacle on the left

To communicate the relevant information between the snow groomer simulation and the haptic devices, Haption designed and implemented a custom communication protocol allowing the TTC Central Processing Unit to exchange information with the Haptics ECU controller via a TCP connection (see Figure 15 below). This protocol is described in more detail in deliverable D5.3 “*Visualization and Interaction Infrastructure (final version)*”.

Figure 15: Messaging protocol for the communication between Haptics ECU and TTC CPU

Furthermore, for the purposes of prototyping haptics functions, Creanex made available a set of simulators in- and output data over a UDP socket. Using this, Haption designed a custom software mimicking the information relay functions of the TTC Control Unit, allowing direct connection of a PC running the Creanex snow groomer simulation to the Haptics ECU. Internally, this custom software also implemented the same communication protocol discussed above and described in detail in deliverable D5.3 “Visualization and Interaction Infrastructure (final version)” and shown in Figure 15.

2.1.2.9 Integration of Novel Prototypes on the Snow Groomer

As described in D6.1, we developed three prototypes, i.e., a camera-spotlight setup, a camera-laser setup and a panoramic thermal camera. At our initial tests in Sterzing (IT) in February of 2024, we found that the camera-spotlight setup was not of great interest to the operators. Hence, we did not pursue on developing it further and focused on prototypes of more interest: i.e. the panoramic thermal camera and the camera-laser setup. Compared to the initial prototypes, the ones tested have several improvements: We integrated a visible-light projector in the laser-camera setup, which allows us to not only project laser images but also more expressive content. Moreover, the metal casing is much more robust the initial wooden casing. Furthermore, we extended the panoramic thermal camera with a 360° LiDAR device, allowing us to accurately measure our environment and use it to record data and enhance the localization in the environment with SLAM methods, if the CAN-bus GPS is not sufficiently accurate.

In two integration meetings in Sterzing in January and March 2025, we were able to mount and test the prototypes on a real snow groomer. As depicted in Figure 16, the panoramic thermal camera is mounted atop the metal case of the camera-laser setup.

Figure 16: Panoramic thermal camera mounted on snow groomer

We were able to successfully project localized primitives with the camera-laser prototype on the ski slope. To enable a projection to be at a fixed place at the slope, we need to be localised within the environment. For this, we utilize the CAN-bus, as it contains the GPS data and feed this information into our Unity application. This is visualized in the left picture at Figure 17, where we show a screenshot of our reconstruction and the pre-defined primitives in Unity, the view from within the cockpit and a drone-shot from the resulting projection. We refer the reader to deliverable 5.7, where we provide video material of our field test.

Figure 17: Laser projection within UC1 (left image simulation, middle and right image real life)

2.1.2.10 Data Handling and Processing Infrastructure

To finally integrate all the technologies into the final demonstrator, a central computing and processing infrastructure is required that can collect all the required data from the relevant sensors and transferring the data again to the available output devices, like haptic or visual outputs. Additionally, the applications that

will interpret the collected data and transform it into understandable and interpretable feedback for the human operator also need to be hosted on the infrastructure. This all needs to be done within the mobile machinery, without being dependent on external computing sources, like cloud infrastructures.

Within Task 5.3 – Visualization Infrastructure and Interaction System, the central computing infrastructure is being developed, including the interfaces for connecting to the other technologies, like visual and haptic feedback devices. This task has been finalized, and the prototypical system has been provided and used for first demonstrators, which will be described below and already first information has also been provided on this in deliverable D5.3. The data coming from the different data sources (e.g., sensors) is mainly coming over the general communication buses available within the snow groomer, which are mainly CAN and Ethernet channels. As the snow groomer is being operated in unknown and harsh environments (snowstorms, cold, white out, etc.), the infrastructure is ruggedized and capable of withstanding various environmental conditions.

As mentioned in deliverable D6.1, the first step for the integration was to integrate the setup in a Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) environment, including a simulated environment. Within the Use Case 1, such a demonstrator was established using a snow groomer cabin, equipped with multiple XR technologies and a simulated environment depicted a skiing area, where the snow groomer can drive around (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Snow groomer HiL environment

The integration of the infrastructure with the other components of the demonstrator and the actual demonstrator was performed in multiple stages. In the first phase, the goal was to integrate as much of the software to be hosted as possible on the platform in advance, before actual meeting at the location of the demonstrator. Interaction with multiple partners have taken place to install the required software/drivers/firmware of the platform, to ensure that the solutions would work when meeting at the use case demonstrator. Left side of Figure 20 shows some of the simulation software running on the hardware and displayed in one of the connected displays. This is one of the functionalities that will be displayed within the cabin for providing an overview of the environment, when the operator is e.g., in a complete white-out. On the right side of Figure 20, the hardware is integrated in the cabin and connected to the internal CAN bus of the cabin, so that data can be transferred to the applications hosted on the platform.

During the last integration meetings that have taken place at Prinoth premises, the final merging of the different hard- and software solutions were performed and the integration in the snow groomer cabin. The data handling infrastructure is at the centre of the demonstrator, as can also be seen in schematic picture of the demonstrator, depicted in Figure 19. The hardware is in direct connection with most of the solutions developed within the project and ensures that data is being provided to the right applications and being handled correctly. Additionally, most of the connections is CAN-based, where also Ethernet is being deployed and additionally, also an MQTT connection for establishing the connection between some solutions.

Figure 19: Schematic overview of components in the UC1 demonstrator

As can be viewed in the schematic overview, the central processor is integrated with the following technologies:

- Simulation environment providing virtual snow grooming environment
- Laser projection
- Panoramic camera
- Active Lightning, using LEDs, highlighting to the operator if some obstacles (i.e., skier) is coming from a specific direction that is not directly in the field of view of the operator
- Haptic Feedback
- Displays showing in-cabin simulation

Figure 20: Integration of data and processing infrastructure in demonstrator

The final demonstrator, which is the actual snow groomer, has been completely finalized and the integration process is still ongoing. Nevertheless, the current demonstrator is a one-to-one copy of a real demonstrator, only with a virtual environment. The architecture of the cabin is identical to the real snow groomer. According to experts at the demonstrator site, the transfer from the demonstrator to the real machine should be straightforward process. This will be the last process in the use case before the final evaluation and validation can be performed.

2.1.3 Conclusions on UC1

The integration work in Use Case 1 demonstrates the successful convergence of XR technologies, multimodal interaction concepts, advanced sensing, and haptic systems into a unified operator-centered platform. Achieved through iterative prototyping in labs, simulators, and real snow groomers, the integration ensured interoperability across diverse hardware and software components, including projection systems, adaptive XR displays, and vibrotactile controls.

Crucially, integration extended beyond the technical layer: user needs, safety-critical requirements, and privacy considerations were systematically embedded through co-design, value-sensitive design, and GDPR-aligned assessments. A central processing infrastructure enabled seamless data flow between sensors, actuators, and XR output devices, ensuring robust performance under demanding environmental conditions.

This integration strategy not only validated the feasibility of XR-enhanced snow grooming operations but also established a transferable framework for embedding XR solutions into other industrial contexts. By bridging simulation and real-world application, the project has shown that integration is the key step for transforming innovative concepts into practical, safe, and ethically responsible technologies.

2.2 Use Case 2 – Logistics

2.2.1 UC2 Infrastructure

Kalmar has test yard in Ljungby Sweden next to KALMAR's Innovation Center offices. Here are some features of the area:

- Fenced test area for automated and autonomous machines.
- Access control on pedestrian gate
- CCTV cameras installed to light poles
- Different kind of containers inside the test area
- Container office for remote control desk

Figure 21: Kalmar automation test yard dimensions and locations at Ljungby Sweden.

Figure 22: RC containers at Kalmar automation test yard.

Figure 23: Remote Connection to reachstacker.

Kalmar made remote control system for reachstacker with Speedgoat RT target HW and it is connected to Kalmar test network which is including test yard also in Finland. So, the machine can be controlled also from Finland.

2.2.2 Integrated Technologies/Methodologies

2.2.2.1 Application of Co-Design Methodology in UC2

Due to the transdisciplinary co-design approach running in roughly the same way and timespan in all use-cases, this section will be mostly identical to Section 2.1.2.1, only deviating in dates and details of the process. Following the user research conducted in Hanko, Finland, and Ljungby, Sweden, as part of T3.1, a problem scenario was defined (first step of the scenario-based design approach), describing a current typical reach stacker operation. This scenario was shared with the consortium. On December 15, 2023, an ideation workshop was held involving all active partners in this use-case. In this workshop, ideas for technology usage and some concepts already in development were collected and discussed in terms of their technical feasibility and expected utility for the operators. It was assumed that operators may have difficulties coming up with technology usage and interaction ideas on their own and may both over- and underestimate what is currently technically possible. Thus, the input from project partners was going to be implemented into a first activity scenario version, providing examples of how XR technology could realistically support operators at work and serving as a basis for the idea generation and validation with operators.

For explanations of the naming and background of realistic and futuristic vision scenario, see Section 2.1.2.1. The first version of the realistic and futuristic vision scenarios for UC2 were completed and shared with the consortium in January 2024. Subsequently, the planning of co-design workshops with operators started in coordination with KAL and VTT. An external partner from the logistics domain interested in participating in the co-design process was acquired in summer 2024. First co-design workshops for ideating technologies and interaction concepts for reach stacker remote control desks with real operators from Euroports Hanko, Finland, were started in July 2024 and were completed by November 2024.

After a break of several months, where the focus was placed on use cases 1 and 3, the co-design process in UC2 resumed in June 2025. The next stage resulted in text-based information scenarios, complemented by wireframes (rough visualisations of XR- and screen-based information), partly using screenshots from VTT's simulation environment. The final stage of the scenario-based co-design approach followed immediately afterwards and involved the ideation and validation of positive user experience (PUX) concepts and providing safety-critical design recommendations in the final integrated interaction scenarios (see deliverable D3.7). This stage was completed in June 2025. With the finalization of deliverable D3.7, the scenario-based co-

design process (task T3.2) has concluded in UC2, final work on the prototypes is being done (task T3.4) and evaluations (task T3.5) are being planned.

2.2.2.2 Information Requirements and Multimodal Interaction Concepts

The same analysis and conceptualization approach as in UC1 (see 1.2.2.2) was applied in this use case.

Information requirements were analysed through conducting a **system analysis**, a **task analysis** and an **interaction sequence analysis** of reach stackers and reach stacker operation (see Deliverable 4.1 and 4.3). Analysis resulted in a comprehensive list of information and interaction requirements for snow groomer machine control, operation activities based on identified high level goals (Task fulfilment/effectivity, Machine efficiency, Ensure Safety and Machine operability) and attention locations for selected operation sequences. For UC2, these requirements comprise of for example information about (hidden) objects in the vicinity (amount, orientation, distance, type, and movement of the obstacles), navigation and location information (e.g. container current and target position, manoeuvre areas and movement paths), load charts of picked containers, and information about the position and configuration of the picker to precisely realizing the container lock. Conventional approaches in reach stacker operation require operators to use direct sight on the environment, picker and container. In teleoperation scenarios, this sight is represented through camera streams that can be augmented with spatially aligned digital information such as maps, 3D data, and virtual tool positioning information, presented on the display screens of the teleoperation environment.

Attention constraints were identified by conducting **analysis of operation tasks** in reachstacker revealing significant amounts of attention allocation lay on four attention hot spots: (1) the terrain around the reach stacker, (2) the picker, (3) the container, and (4) the joysticks/vibration/sound in the cabin, that provide haptic feedback about the machines load. Operators continuously shift attention between these in operation procedures.

Opportunities and Constraints of XR technologies were assessed in discussing technical capabilities of multi-perspective video augmentation with spatially aligned visuals and extended haptic feedback technologies regarding their capabilities to effectively augment real world information and digital data at attentional hot spots in these operation scenarios. Accounting for the identified areas of attention allocation in the reach stacker use case, we explored three XR technologies and their information presentation and interaction capabilities and constraints:

- **Ground and area projections:** Dynamic and spatially mapped projections in the environment offer the capability to present high complex graphical information directly at points of interest. We found that such visualizations can be used to visualize navigation instructions, navigation paths, area restrictions, objects and obstacles in the environment, and range limitations of the picker boom regarding the vehicles current position. However, augmenting visuals can impair the view on the environment and should either be placed in uncritical areas, use simple and less expansive visual objects and may be controllable regarding their appearance and position.
- **Picker and container projections:** Information that are important in container picking, moving and placing tasks may benefit from a presentation through augmenting overlays on the picker and container, as operator's pay a lot of attention to this place. We found that **picker and container projections** might be useful to present information from object detection algorithms to provide better visibility of obstacles. Overlaying data from a virtual 3D-model that visualizes hidden environment as well as a bird view perspective showing alignment between picker and container could further facilitate operation performance and safety.
- **Haptic control feedback:** Haptic feedback in the reach stacker boom control joystick offers more realistic feedback and may contribute to significantly improve immersiveness of teleoperation environments. We found that this XR modality can be used to inform operators about required or restricted machine and picker movements. Further, haptic and force feedback on physical controls

can reinforce or reproduce machine behaviour, which can improve accuracy and operation performance in teleoperation environments.

Based on these insights, **multimodal interaction concepts** defined interaction and information presentation modalities that combine specific real-world information and digital data at distinct places in the cabin-based control environment. The conducted analysis highlighted the problem of increasing complexity and importance of display-based information while environment-based or backed information also stays important forcing the operator to constantly shift attention. Combining different modalities in XR features aims to help to reduce the ease of use and complexity of display-based interfaces or to move information from display-based interfaces to environmental perception. In exploring this design space in between information requirements and XR technology opportunities we defined a final interaction concept for UC2 that comprises the following features:

- **Ground Projections**, [Lab/SIM, Machine] are used to explore effective visualization techniques to present, navigational aids, highlighting detected objects as well as conveying collision warnings. Navigation aids can be visualized as instructions (distance, direction). Paths and borders can be visualized as graphics (arrows, numeric indicators, lines and shaded shapes).
- **Picker and container projections** [Lab/ Machine] are used to highlight detected objects in available video streams as well as augmenting 3D pit models with live terrain data (LiDAR) regarding surface profile and textures to ease aligning virtual models with the perceived environment. Also, above and sub-surface objects are visualized in the augmented virtual 3D-model.
- **Haptic control feedback** [Lab] is realized to provide realistic force feedback for boom and tool control. Further, vibratory feedback signals are implemented that indicate warning and movement limits.
- **Adaptable XR techniques** [Lab] are realized to explore usefulness of giving operators the ability to navigate across the spectrum between full reality and maximum augmentation with virtual information to account for different situational and individual requirements. Two approaches to adaptation controls were conceptualized: (1) a GUI-based setup environment that operators can use to manipulate the XR features, and (2) a set of hardware controls placed in the cabin. Both approaches allow operators to change the presentation of augmenting data on each XR output device regarding virtuality/reality (e.g. though changing opacity or brightness), level of detail and coverage of assistive systems (e.g., obstacle detection).

2.2.2.3 Identifying Privacy Requirements and Strategies for Mitigating Privacy and Ethical Risks in Implementations in UC2

To identify the possible risks for privacy and ethics in UC2 we used the following technologies:

- A series of questions in the semi-structured interviews [5] with the operators were performed in the frames of co-design workshops and conducted as part of T3.1 (similarly to the procedure described in 2.1.2.4) of the operations and new data modalities provided by XR.
- Based on the UC 2 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.2.2.1), we developed and conducted two iterative [10] workshops with the end-users using the approach based on value-sensitive design [3]. In the first workshop, we proposed to the end-users the list of Schwartz values [7] and discussed with them the importance of these values to their work as reach stacker operator, using the fictional reach stacker operator persona; in addition, we tested the perception of each technology, validated in the frames of co-design, in the dimensions of usefulness, ease of use (subdomains of Technology Acceptance Model [2]), security/safety [8] and excitement([6]) (similarly to UC1).

On the second stage, based on the most important values, we started to discuss how the violation of these values in design can affect the perception of the work and what should be done in the scenario to ensure that this "anti-scenario" (negative scenario of using technology [4]) will not take place. As the UC2 imply the future transition from in-person to distant operation, our negative scenarios in UC2 tried to capture and discuss the value-related aspects in both aspects.

At the same line as in UC1, we are planning to prototype the two mechanisms, which can support the values of autonomy and security on the interface level and make the final user evaluation of the concepts in October 2025. As the discussion of the security value in the presented UC shifted towards a discussion of technological solutions to the discussion about the operators' education, in this case, we are planning to tailor prototyping to support the autonomy value and discuss the educational recommendations supporting security as an additional goal.

- Based on the UC2 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.2.2.1), we developed a survey of privacy questions for the stakeholders regarding each of the proposed changes in the basic workflow, using the principles of Data Protection Impact Assessment. The questionnaire helped identify the most privacy-critical parts of the proposed technology development and added privacy concerns to the discussion about the feasibility of proposed solutions. Besides eliciting GDPR-related requirements, we applied the LINDDUN GO methodology [9] to elicit a broader range of technical and non-technical privacy concerns from stakeholders. To do that, we organised two privacy workshops with representatives of UC2 and technological partners involved in UC2. In addition, we conducted a focus group with the members of the consortium, involved in all cases specifically dedicated to the use of AI on the project level (see 2.1.2.4 for more information).

Also based on the work with the end-users and other stakeholders, described in D7.4 we designed the list of Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Designing the XR implementations (see 2.1.2.4 for more information).

2.2.2.4 Augmented Reality via 360° Video Feed

The remote visualization system consists of multiple elements, namely:

- 2 cameras with a 360-degree field of view
- 3 PCs: one running Nokia's RXRM streaming system, one running the computer vision application developed by VTT, and one that runs the visualization application also developed by VTT
- 2 5G modems inside that are in the same virtual network and connect the remote device to the PCs in the reach stacker's cabin

The first two computers are meant to be placed inside the reach stacker's cabin (in our case, in Ljungby), while the latter is meant to be used remotely (in our case, in Tampere). Because of technical reasons, the streams are retrieved from the cameras by the RXRM PC, which then streams the footage to both the remote PC and the local one for computer vision. The computer vision PC then elaborates the video stream to detect people from every camera, reconstruct a scene of the reach stacker and the people surrounding it, and it finally sends this spatial information to the remote PC which then overlays UI on top of the streamed footage by using the Unity game engine.

Figure 24: Final system architecture for streaming the video, performing computer vision and reconstructing the scene on a remote PC.

Each camera only needs to be calibrated once. Since the cameras have a 360-degree field of view, traditional calibration methods are not viable (they require less than 180-degree FOV). We have thus developed a system that leverages linear regression to calibrate and estimate the distance of tracked objects given the assumptions that such objects touch the ground. The calibration process was smoothed out so that, after taking a picture with the camera at a specified know height, the user can manually drag and position the green lines on the image on top of the markers. Once done, the system produces a JSON file that can later be read to fit the regression curve and estimate the object’s distance in real time with minimal computation power.

Figure 25: Calibration process. Markers are places around the camera. The user can drag the green lines to align them to the markers on the ground. The system will generate a JSON file with the data required to fit the linear regression curve for distance estimation.

The result of the calibration process consists in the reconstruction of a shared knowledge across the cameras, so that object detections can be highlighted in a camera footage even when occluded by another object (given that the detection is visible by at least another camera). This feature aims to increase safety on the workplace and helps the operator’s cope with an otherwise reduced situational awareness when operating remotely. In the image below, a reconstruction of VTT’s lab can be seen as a 2D map, which also represents the knowledge shared between the cameras. Next to the map, there are camera footages from a 360-degree

camera and a webcam, showing detections both from the camera itself and the reconstruction of the detection from the other camera.

Figure 26: Shared knowledge between cameras. Detections from the 360-degree camera are in blue, and from the webcam in red. In the first image, both cameras perform the detection (there are 2 circles in the map, and 2 bounding boxes are drawn on the streams). In the second image, only one camera is able to perform the detection (only blue circle and bounding box), but the system is able to render it also on the webcam thanks to the reconstructed shared knowledge.

As described at the beginning of this section, most of the hardware used for this system will be implemented inside the reachstacker cabin. One camera will be placed on top of the vehicle’s spreader, and the other one will be placed inside the cabin, to give a view that is as close as possible to the one operator have when operating on site. Both cameras require Power Over Ethernet (PoE). Both the RXRM PC and the computer-vision laptop will be placed inside the cabin, together with the 5G modem. Since the reach stacker will be stationary for this demo, electricity from the grid might be used instead of the battery pack shown in the schema below.

Figure 27: Hardware setup on the reach stacker. Everything will be inside the cabin, except for the Nokia360 camera which will be placed on top of the vehicle’s spreader.

The view inside the Unity application features virtually the same UI and visualization mechanics that were used for the simulator, with the difference that a real streamed video footage is shown instead of a 3D virtual environment, with a load chart to help operators keep the container in a safe position, and UI hints to highlight detected people, even when they are partially or completely occluded by another object.

Figure 28: Remote visualization. The application makes use of the same UI that was developed and refined through the simulator, with only minor differences and refinements.

2.2.2.5 Haptic Control

Haption's Virtuose 6D device was used to simulate a force-feedback-enabled joystick. The joystick mapping follows the real reach stacker control system, with the x-axis controlling the boom extension, and the y-axis controlling the boom angle.

During the third user test that was held in VTT's premises on Feb 27th, 2024, users were able to try a force feedback feature where the joystick forward rotation (that rotates the boom downwards) would block when the container touched the ground (or the target truck's flatbed). Users provided overall positive feedback about the feature, even though the testing time for that was very short and there wasn't a specified goal to the task, but rather to move the spreader around and feel the force feedback. Future developments could involve making the user feel the weight and torque applied to the reachstacker by the container, as well as proximity of the container to other containers when the container needs to be placed in a tight space between other containers.

Figure 29: Integrating a Virtuose6D haptic interface with the UC2 simulator

Initially, to interface a 6DoF haptic feedback device with VTT’s unity simulation, a dedicated “HapticServer” software running as a Windows service was prototyped in the context of deliverables D3.4 “*Low-fidelity XR prototypes*” and D4.8 “*Interaction Concepts (final version)*” (see Figure 30). This software handles low-level configuration and control of the haptic device via Haption’s dedicated API, while also ensuring that the high-frequency control data for the haptic device is made available at the correct rate based on the low-frequency input data from the simulation. Since both software components implement very similar functionality, the software’s final internal architecture closely resembles that of the firmware running on the Haptics ECU for the purposes of UC1, with communication towards a client also happening over an on-machine TCP connection using a flexible and extensible protocol based on Google Flatbuffers³.

³ <https://flatbuffers.dev/>

Figure 30: Functional diagram for the HapticServer background service

Ultimately, we designed a generic client for the “HapticServer” inside Unity3D, allowing any Unity-based simulation to connect to a Haption haptic input device, to retrieve input control data, and to request haptic behaviours (see Figure 31). This client was used for the final prototyping of haptic functions for use-case UC2 in the Haption simulator based on the Unity simulation initially provided by VTT. This simulation and the haptics functions in question are described in detail in deliverable D4.8 “Interaction Concepts (final version)”.

Figure 31: Structure of the HapticServer client in the Unity simulation

2.2.2.6 3D Sound for better situation awareness

All of the 360 cameras used in this project are capable of transmitting both video and audio. In addition to capturing panoramic video, each camera can stream audio directly to the user through the RTSP (Real-Time Streaming Protocol). This ensures that users not only receive a complete 360-degree visual experience but also the corresponding sound in real time, using the same protocol for an easier integration.

2.2.2.7 Gesture-based UI Control

The hand tracking gestures, and visual feedback implemented in this version are consistent with those introduced in the simulator presented in the previous deliverables. Specifically, the user can perform a pinch gesture with the left hand and move it in the 3D space to rotate the camera view or use a swipe gesture with the left hand to switch between the video streams from the different available cameras. The visual feedback system informs the user about the current status of the tracking system, where 2 vertical arrows pointing inwards mean that the pinch gesture is currently active, and 2 horizontal arrows pointing outwards indicate the swipe gesture is ready to be activated is the user quickly moves their hand either left or right. A 3D “dome” shows the virtual boundaries used by the application to track the user’s hand, so that gestures cannot be accidentally activated outside of boundaries.

Figure 32: Hand-tracking feedback tool. This system was presented and refined for the simulator, and it was also adapted for the real-time video streaming system.

2.2.3 Conclusions on UC2

The implementation of the described technologies will take place in Ljungby, Sweden, on 25–26 September 2025, where they will be applied directly to a Kalmar reach stacker. This marks a significant transition from laboratory testing to real-world deployment. In this section, we introduced the core technologies—Augmented Reality via 360° video feed with people tracking, haptic control, 3D spatial sound, and gesture-based UI control—all designed to enhance situational awareness and operator interaction. Their integration into the Kalmar reach stacker represents a pivotal milestone in validating the system’s performance under operational conditions when teleoperator is controlling the machine with remote control desk.

2.3 Use Case 3 – Construction

2.3.1 UC3 Infrastructure

Infrastructure involved in the research and development activities regarding UC3 comprised the TUDs interaction lab, a construction machinery test facility (also TUD) as well as an operator training centre that supported us in requirement analysis workshops and technology evaluation activities. Research and Testing in the **interaction Lab** was used to prototype the light feedback and matrix display technology. Further visuals for ground projection and adaptable XR were tested as well in the context of excavator operation scenarios using XR output hardware but simulated work environment and sensor data. The **construction machinery test facility** was used to equip XR technologies and required sensors to our test excavator. Technical feasibility, functionality was tested as well as evaluative user studies conducted. The **operator training centre** helped us with feedback, domain expertise and participants for co-creation workshops and evaluation testing.

2.3.2 Integrated Technologies/Methodologies

2.3.2.1 Application of Co-Design Methodology in UC3

Due to the transdisciplinary co-design approach running in roughly the same way and timespan in all use-cases, this section will be mostly identical to 2.1.2.1, only deviating in dates and details of the process. Following the user research conducted in Dresden and Glauchau, Germany, as part of T3.1, a problem scenario was defined (first step of the scenario-based design approach), describing a current typical excavator operation. This scenario was shared with the consortium. On October 20, 2023, an ideation workshop was held involving all active partners in this use-case. In this workshop, ideas for technology usage and some concepts already in development were collected and discussed in terms of their technical feasibility and expected utility for the operators. It was assumed that operators may have difficulties coming up with technology usage and interaction ideas on their own and may both over- and underestimate what is currently technically possible. Thus, the input from project partners was going to be implemented into a first activity scenario version, providing examples of how XR technology could realistically support operators at work and serving as a basis for the idea generation and validation with operators.

The first version of realistic and futuristic vision scenario for UC3 were completed and shared with the consortium in January 2024. Subsequently, the planning of co-design workshops with operators started in coordination with TUD and the ÜAZ Glauchau, a construction machinery training centre that had been acquired as supporting partner in summer 2023. The first stage of co-design workshops, focusing on validating and expanding planned technological features (e. g., usage of light bars for information visualization in the front window frame or laser projections of hidden structures into the construction trench), was completed in March 2024 (see Figure 33).

Figure 33: Picture from the visit to the ÜAZ Glauchau training area in March 2024

The next stage of co-design workshops for UC3, validating and elaborating information design concepts, was completed in May 2024. This stage resulted in text-based information scenarios, complemented by wireframes (rough visualisations of XR- and screen-based information), partly using screenshots and design resources from TUD. The final stage of the scenario-based co-design approach involved the ideation and validation of positive user experience (PUX) concepts and providing safety-critical design recommendations in the final integrated interaction scenarios (see deliverable D3.7). This stage was completed within a final workshop in June 2025. With the finalization of deliverable D3.7, the scenario-based co-design process (task T3.2) has concluded in UC3, final work on the prototypes is being done (task T3.4) and evaluations (task T3.5)

are in progress. To support in the evaluations, another regional construction training centre in Geradstetten, Germany, was contacted and acquired as an external partner in summer 2025 (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Picture from the visit to the Geradstetten construction training centre in June 2025

2.3.2.2 Information Requirements and Multimodal Interaction Concepts

The same analysis and conceptualization approach as in UC1 and UC2 was applied in this use case again.

For UC3, these requirements comprise of for example information about (hidden) objects in the vicinity (amount, orientation, distance, type, and movement of the obstacles), sub-surface objects (e.g. soil below the snow or pipes and rubble in construction sites), maps and 3D-data to inform themselves about the current state of the environment to a planned target state. In use cases 3 (construction), this involves moving soil to create a planned surface geometry. In use cases 3 this transformation involves information about the position (work depth) of the tool (e.g., bucket) to precisely realizing the target geometry. Conventional approaches require operators to use maps, 3D data, and tool position information, presented on the terminal display to inform themselves about the accuracy of their current vehicle and tool movement.

Analysing attention allocation within these excavator operating tasks revealed 4 locations of interest: (1) the tool that is monitored to ensure accurate positioning, movement and fill level, (2) the close environment to monitor effects of soil movement regarding a planned target geometry, (3) the wider environment to check for obstacles, (4) the display terminal to monitor video streams of the environment and checking digital 3D-models of the target surface, and (5) the joysticks/vibration/sound in the cabin, that provide haptic feedback about the machines load.

XR-Technology opportunities: The main share of operation tasks in UC3 is put on controlling the tool and checking the display is considered a distraction. Thus, we aimed to use XR technologies to bring as much digital information to the environment as possible. Accounting for the identified areas of attention allocation we explored six XR technologies and their information presentation and interaction **capabilities and constraints:**

- **Light Feedback System:** Peripheral light feedback brings the opportunity to communicate low-complex information from outside the attention focus area. Different spatial setups were explored finding that ambient light feedback from a light strip around the windshield could be used to indicate position, distance, and type of detected obstacles, indicating deviation of actual tool height to target pit depth as well as indicating distance between tool and planned pit boundaries. Light feedback is very limited regarding the complexity of information that can be conveyed, needs to be adjusted to environmental light conditions and can distract the operator.
- **Matrix Display:** Matrix displays can be very robust and provide high visibility (brightness) with the cost of low graphical resolution. We found that a matrix display mounted close to the shovel can be used to present sub-surface objects below the bucket, the deprivation of the current tool position to target depth and geometry as well as the position and distance of objects in the vicinity. Constraints of matrix displays are the low resolution that challenge visualization designs. As the matrix cannot be installed on the bucket (the main point of attention allocation) their presented information must be detected and identified also in peripheral perception, further limiting the complexity of information that can be conveyed.
- **Laser Projection:** Dynamic and spatially mapped laser projections in the environment offer the capability to present high complex graphical information directly at point of interest. We found that such visualizations can be used to visualize sub-surface pipes, 3D geometry data (e.g. deviation from actual surface to profile to target surface profile for a larger area) as a coloured grid or a linear cross section as well as to visualize planned movement paths, navigation instructions, pit geometry and range limitations of the excavators boom regarding the vehicles current position. However, laser projections are limited in brightness and higher levels of brightness come with increased safety risks (eye damage). Experimenting with a level 4 laser in day-light conditions revealed that laser projections might be too risky in often crowded construction sites.
- **Display AR:** Terminal displays offer the opportunity to augment video streams and virtual 3D models blending virtual data with real world information cues. We found that display-based augmentation might be useful to augment video streams stemming from an array of conventional and thermal cameras with information from object detection algorithms to providing better visibility of obstacles. Overlaying data from a virtual 3D-model that visualizes pick-up and drop-off locations, setoffs between current and target tool position and target pit geometry on camera streams as well as augmenting virtual 3D models with live LiDAR data can help operators to understand such digital information. Augmented video streams can also be used to present interactive load charts. Limitations in using display-based augmentation lay in the fact, that operators need to divert their attention from the actual pit to the terminal display, thus making this XR technology more suitable for more extensive briefing and setup routines than for assisting operators during tool movement activities.
- **Haptic control feedback:** Haptic feedback in the excavators' joysticks offer the opportunity to present feedback cues at a place where the operator has its hands most of the time. We found that this XR modality can be used to inform operators about required or restricted tool movement. Further, haptic and force feedback on physical controls can reinforce or reproduce machine behaviour, which can also be used to inform the excavator operator about limits in tool movement or the distance to target tool positions.

Multimodal Interaction Concepts: This analysis highlighted the problem of increasing complexity and importance of display-based information while environment-based or backed information also stays important forcing the operator to constantly shift attention. Combining different modalities in XR features aims to help to reduce the ease of use and complexity of display-based interfaces or to move information from display-based interfaces to environmental perception. In exploring this design space in between information requirements and XR technology opportunities we defined a final interaction concept for UC3 that comprises the following features:

- **Light-Feedback Systems** [Lab/SIM, Machine] were realized to cover the forward windscreen and the terminal display to provide peripheral information when looking onto the tool and environment as well as when interacting with the terminal display. This XR modality is used to present information regarding detected objects (above and sub-surface) in the environment and deviation of tool position to target pit geometry. Objects are visualized as light indications highlighting the direction (as by position on the light strip) and distance (as by the colour of the light indication). Position deviations are represented as linear bars in x and y orientation to show distance in rotation and depth of the tool.
- **A Matrix Display** [Lab/SIM, Machine] mounted on the stick close to the bucket to show information closer to the area of attention allocation when controlling the tool (bucket). This XR modality is used to present information regarding detected objects (above and sub-surface) in the environment and deviation of tool position to target pit geometry. Objects are visualized as light indications highlighting the direction (as by position on the light strip) and distance (as by the colour of the light indication). Position deviations are represented as linear bars in x and y orientation to show distance in rotation and depth of the tool.
- **AR Display Visualizations** [Lab/ Machine] are used to highlight detected objects in available video streams as well as augmenting 3D pit models with live terrain data (LiDAR) regarding surface profile and textures to ease aligning virtual models with the perceived environment. Also, above and sub-surface objects are visualized in the augmented virtual 3D-model.
- **Ground Projections**, [Lab/SIM] even though not feasible in the real environment, are used in the lab demonstrator to explore effective visualization techniques to present surface deviation from target geometry as well as detected above and sub-surface objects. Insights in feasible visualization techniques are considered useful for advanced glasses-based AR visualizations that may be achieved when AR glasses technology becomes more suitable for hour-long work shifts.
- **Adaptable XR techniques** [Lab] are realized to explore usefulness of giving operators the ability to navigate across the spectrum between full reality and maximum augmentation with virtual information to account for different situational and individual requirements. Two approaches to adaptation controls were conceptualized: (1) a GUI-based setup environment that operators can use to manipulate the XR features, and (2) a set of hardware controls placed in the cabin. Both approaches allow operators to change the presentation of augmenting data on each XR output device regarding virtuality/reality (e.g. though changing opacity or brightness), level of detail and coverage of assistive systems (e.g., obstacle detection, target pit geometry).

2.3.2.3 Identifying Privacy Requirements and Strategies for Mitigating Privacy and Ethical Risks in Implementations in UC3

To identify the possible risks for privacy and ethics in UC3 we used the following technologies:

- A series of questions in the semi-structured interviews [5] with the operators were performed in the frames of co-design workshops and conducted as part of T3.1 (similarly to the procedure described in 2.1.2.4) of the operations and new data modalities provided by XR.
- Based on the UC 3 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.3.2.1), we developed two and conducted one iterative [10] workshop with the end-users using the approach based on value-sensitive design [3]. In the first workshop, we proposed to the end-users the list of Schwartz values [7] and discussed with them the importance of these values to their work as excavator operator, using the fictional operator persona; in addition, we tested the perception of each technology, validated in the frames of co-design, in the dimensions of usefulness, ease of use (subdomains of Technology Acceptance Model [2]), security/safety [8] and excitement([6]) (similarly to UC1).

On the second stage, which will be conducted in September 2025, we plan to present the most important identified values to the operators. When we plan to discuss how the violation of these values in design can affect the perception of the work and what should be done in the scenario to ensure that this "anti-scenario" (negative scenario of using technology [4]) will not take place.

At the same line as in UC1, we are planning to prototype the two mechanisms, which can support the values of autonomy and security on the interface level and make the final user evaluation of the concepts in November 2025. As the construction professionals' community is present on the crowdsourcing platforms, we are planning to make a large-scale evaluation of the concepts and the variables, contributing to the acceptance of ethical and privacy-supporting mechanisms.

- Based on the UC3 scenarios, finalised in the frames of the co-design approach (2.3.2.1), we developed a survey of privacy questions for the stakeholders regarding each of the proposed changes in the basic workflow, using the principles of Data Protection Impact Assessment. The questionnaire helped identify the most privacy-critical parts of the proposed technology development and added privacy concerns to the discussion about the feasibility of proposed solutions. Besides eliciting GDPR-related requirements, we applied the LINDDUN GO methodology [9] to elicit a broader range of technical and non-technical privacy concerns from stakeholders. To do that, we organised privacy workshops with representatives of UC3 and technological partners involved in UC3 (we made only one workshop in this UC as several problems discussed in the frames of this workshop were already discussed in a similar UC1 workshop). In addition, we conducted a focus group with the members of the consortium, involved in all cases specifically dedicated to the use of AI on the project level (see 2.1.2.4 for more information).

Also based on the work with the end-users and other stakeholders, described in D7.4 we designed the list of Guidelines for Privacy and Ethics for Designing the XR implementations (see 2.1.2.4 for more information).

2.3.2.4 Excavator Simulator

A virtual version of the ambient LED bars was implemented in the simulator. In the same way as in the snow groomer simulator, it visualises the direction and distance of detected obstacles. Animated walking construction worker can be set to walk around the machine while operator is excavating. The simulator has outgoing signals for detected obstacle distances and headings, which can be transmitted via CAN or UDP to the real physical version of the LED bar. This way a real LED bar can react to the virtual obstacles in the simulator.

A virtual version of the LED matrix display developed by TUD was implemented in the simulator. A display indicates the height of the bucket relative to the target height at that position. The display is placed at the end of the boom near the bucket so that the height information is easily visible without the operator having to move their eyes away from the bucket.

The simulator has outgoing signals for the bucket inclination, target inclination and bucket's distance to target, which can be transmitted over CAN. This data can be used by the real physical LED matrix to visualise the height.

Figure 35: Bucket edge (blue) above an inclined target surface (orange)

Figure 36: Bucket edge is at the target height, indicated by the green arrows

A virtual laser projector can be used to highlight underground pipes and other underground obstacles on the surface.

Figure 37: Underground pipe visualised on the surface

2.3.2.5 Data Handling and Processing Infrastructure

Similarly to the data handling and processing infrastructure for UC1 (snow groomer), the same approach is applied for UC3 (excavator). Also, here the aim is to be able to process a certain amount of data directly on the machine and not being dependent on external computing resources.

Within the excavator, already a main controller is available performing already some of the processing. So, the decision was made, that the developed central processor will be integrated with the main controller, as depicted in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Schematic overview of components in the UC3 demonstrator

Nevertheless, a big part of the solution for UC3 will be connected to the central processor, namely the collection of information around the excavator for detecting people that are not visible to the human operator (using Ethernet cameras). The data collected from the cameras is processed directly on the central processor (functioning as an edge device on the machine) and uses a Yolo application to detect the location of the humans around the machine and their distance to the machine. Finally, this information is then transferred to the active lighting solutions that are mounted on the windscreen and the display within the cabin.

Now of writing this deliverable, this is still integration work in progress and is currently being integrated into the excavator in the final process. The final solution will be demonstrated in the upcoming work package 6 deliverables.

2.3.3 Integration into hybrid demonstrator

The novel technologies for the excavator use case have been integrated into a simulation-based demonstrator which also features real hardware elements to extend the user experiences beyond pure simulation. The demonstrator has been developed in course of the Bauma fair and demonstrated the THEIA^{XR} Technologies in an interactive way. This simulator allows to dig with the virtual model of the excavator of TU Dresden, a Case WX 185 with original joysticks from a construction machine. The scene consists of a pit, which must be dug out to a certain height. The main Display of the machine control and the 3D-machine control system is present as a physical device, so that the operator can use it as in a real excavator. With the help of the emulated 3d machine control system, the task of digging to a user-defined height can be experienced. The indication of the height derivation is shown on the main GUI, the LED-matrix display as a virtual asset in the simulation and as a physical device on the boom. Seeing the LED-matrix display as a physical component, helps to reduce the sim2real gap in terms of user experience. Another physical component is the LED-stripe around the front facing window. The window in that case is the monitor which shows the view of the simulated environment. The LED-indicator visualizes the distance and angle of a virtual character that walks around the scene. The operator sees the construction worker also in the virtual rear and side-facing cameras of the excavator that can be shown in the main display. For this demonstrator, the decision felt on to use a virtual person walking around the scene to feed the LED-stripe instead of a real camera mounted on the booth. The real camera would see the operator and a lot of people in the background (at least on the fair) which would result in a densely illuminated LED-stripe. The last technology that is used in this demonstrator is the virtual lidar which scans the virtual scene. This information is used in the main display to visualize the colour coded height map.

Figure 39: Hybrid demonstrator of the excavator use case, featuring both virtual contents and physical elements.

2.3.4 Integration into real excavator

The THEIA^{XR} components have been integrated into a 20t excavator, a WX 185 (Figure 40). The excavator is a wheeled excavator without any assistance or surveying systems preinstalled. Hence, the sensor equipment must be retrofitted to the machine. This comprises of the kinematic sensors, i.e. inertia measurement units on cabin, boom, stick and rocker, as well as a rotary encoder on the slewing gear. An additional pair of GNSS-antennas complements the components for a conventional 3d-machine control system. A 10"-touch display has been installed on the A-pillar to provide a comprehensive graphical user interface for the operator. The information about the current height difference is visualized on the main display as in a conventional 3d machine control system, but also on an LED-matrix display on the bottom side of the stick (Figure 43).

As the excavator had no cameras to monitor the rear and the sides of the machines, three cameras with a field of view of 120° have been installed on the upper carriage. These cameras are used for the AI-based person detection. The cameras have been mounted to cover the relevant area of risks according to industry standards. An LED-stripe has been installed around the front facing, top window in a U-shape. The left camera

feeds the left side of the stripe, the rear camera the bottom side and the right camera feeds the right side of the LED-stripe (Figure 41).

On the top of the cabin, facing the area of work, a solid-state-lidar has been mounted. This lidar scans the area of work during digging and creates a height map during slewing (Figure 42).

Figure 40: Operators view from the excavator on the THEIA^{XR} technologies

Figure 41: Visualization of a person in the vicinity of the excavator via the light feedback system

Figure 42: Visualization of actual surface in side view to support the operator in dig2height tasks or finish grading

Figure 43: LED-matrix display to visualize height derivation directly in the field of view of the operator.

2.3.5 Conclusions on UC3

Three major THEIA^{XR} technologies have been implemented in different demonstrators for the use case 3. A simulation environment, a portable hybrid demonstrator consisting of physical and virtual components and a prototype machine. These demonstrators already served to shape the concrete implementation, assess the feasibility in user studies and showcase the technologies on fairs and events in an interactive way. The simulator and the hybrid demonstrator are well suited to assess the developed THEIA^{XR}-technologies in a user study. They are mobile, easy to use and the evaluation tasks can be performed without additional implementation efforts. The real excavator has the biggest fidelity of all demonstrators and can be used to showcase the THEIA^{XR} technologies in a real-life scenario. Unfortunately, the outdoor test area for the excavator is not suited to simulate the scenarios that are used in the user evaluation, that involve extensive

digging and dangerous situations (persons in the vicinity of the machine). The excavator is mainly used to present the technologies to users without performing dedicated tasks. As a conclusion, the authors state, that the hybrid simulator with VR-content and physical devices was best suited to evaluate and test the different concept in the design phase with real users. It is also a good option to be used for user evaluations because the tasks can be easily designed, and the physical elements give a sufficient feeling of realism. The simulation itself is very portable and can be used to showcase the final implementation to a broad audience and perform a low-threshold test environment. The real excavator is the most impressive demonstrator, features all the technologies in full scale but is the most labor-intensive and costly of all the demonstrators.

3 Conclusions

This deliverable D6.4 provides an overview of the integration activities within the use cases that were performed since the submission of the predecessor deliverable D6.1. The activities described in this deliverable are all related to the work required to integrate the final developed technologies coming from WP3 – WP5. Unfortunately, not all integration activities are finalized yet and some of them still will take place after the submission of this deliverable. They will be described in the upcoming deliverables of the related work package WP6. Majority of the technologies have been first tested in lab settings or cabin setup, before the final integration has taken place into the final machines. The experiences from the integration activities and tests and from the final demonstrations (which will be described in deliverable D6.5) have provided valuable input and feedback to the technical work packages where the technologies were developed. These technical work packages have now also been finalized, so now developments on the technologies are taken place anymore.

The deliverable describes the three use cases individually and highlights the final integration activities for the developed technologies that has been deployed within the specific use case. It highlights the final architecture for the different machinery and how the individual methodologies (Co-Design and Privacy research) and technologies (e.g., laser projection, simulation, computing infrastructure, information display, etc) have been applied and integrated. It describes how they are integrated, or when the final integration is still taking place, how they will be integrated in the final demonstrators.

The demonstrators have been largely finalized in the implementations phase of the project. Some last integration activities are still taking place after the duration of Task 6.1. The final activities will be performed in the remaining of WP6, and will be reported in the respective deliverable D6.5 and D6.6, which are still open deliverables from this work package.

The majority of the developed technologies and methodologies have been implemented in the demonstrators of the three use cases, varying from new sensor technologies, improved simulation environments, new feedback methodologies focusing on immersive visualization and haptic interaction. These technologies have shown great results in the demonstrators and have been presented already so a large selection of operators, external technology providers and OEMs from similar and other domains. The technologies have proven to extract a large interest from entities outside the project and will be used in the remaining part of the project for assessment of the technologies, validation, and for upcoming and future exploitation and dissemination activities to inform a large audience about the final results of the project.

Concluding it can be remarked that the developed and integrated technologies, applied methodologies and selected demonstrators (i.e., snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator) have shown a huge opportunity for integrating new XR based technology and will open many future possibilities for extending these kind of machines and other off-highway mobile machinery with XR technologies that will support the human operator and external people, resulting in more intuitive and safer working environments inside the cabin or in future remote operation.

References

- [1] MARY BETH ROSSON AND JOHN M. CARROLL, 'SCENARIO-BASED DESIGN', IN THE HUMAN-COMPUTER INTERACTION HANDBOOK: FUNDAMENTALS, EVOLVING TECHNOLOGIES AND EMERGING APPLICATIONS, 3RD ED., ANDREW SEARS AND JULIE JACKO, EDS., BOCA RATON: CRC PRESS, 2002, PP. 1032–1050.
- [2] FRED D DAVIS, RICHARD P BAGOZZI, AND PAUL R WARSHAW. 1989. TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL. J MANAG SCI 35, 8 (1989), 982–1003.
- [3] BATYA FRIEDMAN. 1996. VALUE-SENSITIVE DESIGN. INTERACTIONS 3, 6 (1996), 16–23.
- [4] BATYA FRIEDMAN, PETER H KAHN JR, ALAN BORNING, AND ALINA HULDTGREN. 2013. VALUE SENSITIVE DESIGN AND INFORMATION SYSTEMS. IN EARLY ENGAGEMENT AND NEW TECHNOLOGIES: OPENING UP THE LABORATORY. SPRINGER, 55–95.
- [5] SHAZIA JAMSHED. 2014. QUALITATIVE RESEARCH METHOD-INTERVIEWING AND OBSERVATION. JOURNAL OF BASIC AND CLINICAL PHARMACY 5, 4 (2014), 87.
- [6] DOYEON LEE, BYENG-HEE CHANG, AND JISEOB PARK. 2024. VIRTUAL REALITY CONTENT EVALUATION VISUALIZATION TOOL FOCUSED ON COMFORT, CYBERSICKNESS, AND PERCEIVED EXCITEMENT. BEHAVIOUR & INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY 43, 9 (2024), 1859–1878.
- [7] SHALOM H SCHWARTZ. 2012. AN OVERVIEW OF THE SCHWARTZ THEORY OF BASIC VALUES. ONLINE READINGS IN PSYCHOLOGY AND CULTURE 2, 1 (2012), 11.
- [8] IBO VAN DE POEL. 2014. DESIGN FOR VALUES IN ENGINEERING. IN HANDBOOK OF ETHICS, VALUES, AND TECHNOLOGICAL DESIGN. SPRINGER, 1–20.
- [9] KIM WUYTS, LAURENS SION, AND WOUTER JOOSEN. 2020. LINDDUN GO: A LIGHTWEIGHT APPROACH TO PRIVACY THREAT MODELING. IN 2020 IEEE EUROPEAN SYMPOSIUM ON SECURITY AND PRIVACY WORKSHOPS (EUROS&PW). IEEE, 302–309.
- [10] DAVID C WYNN AND CLAUDIA M ECKERT. 2017. PERSPECTIVES ON ITERATION IN DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT. RESEARCH IN ENGINEERING DESIGN 28, 2 (2017) 153–184.
- [11] ROBERTO V ZICARI, JOHN BRODERSEN, JAMES BRUSSEAU, BORIS DÜDDER, TIMO EICHHORN, TODOR IVANOV, GEORGIOS KARARIGAS, PEDRO KRINGEN, MELISSA McCULLOUGH, FLORIAN MÖSLEIN, ET AL . 2021. Z-INSPECTION®: A PROCESS TO ASSESS TRUSTWORTHY AI. IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON TECHNOLOGY AND SOCIETY 2, 2 (2021), 83–97

ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

[API]	Application Programming Interface
[CAN]	Control Area Network
[CPU]	Central Processing Unit
[CCTV]	Closed Circuit Television
[D#.#]	Deliverable #.#
[DoF]	Degree(s) of Freedom
[ECU]	Electronic Control Unit
[I²C]	Inter-Integrated Circuit
[PC]	Personal Computer
[T#.#]	Task #.#
[TCP]	Transmission Control Protocol
[UDP]	User Datagram Protocol
[UI]	User Interface
[USB]	Universal Serial Bus
[WP#]	Work Package #.#
[XR]	eXtended Reality